

Are community policing practices an effective tool to combat VELRT?

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Summary: This paper undertakes a comparison of various community policing approaches to combating radicalisation and violent extremism that lead to terrorism and examines their contrasts and differences.

Key words: Community policing, radicalization, violent extremism, VELRT

Introduction

As communities, governments and nations continue to struggle with the issue of violent extremism and radicalization leading to terrorism, community based policing has again emerged as a potential avenue through which the police can engage with the community, in order to deter, dissuade, detect and counter violence perpetrated by extremists.

When we look for similarities in the motivation or rationale for terrorism or violent extremism, we can see similarities with the motivators that lead to gang violence, which may range from local street gangs to transnational organized crime, with catalysts ranging from religion to regionalism to race.

While the road to violent extremism and terrorism is not exactly the same for any two people, and while it is still not well understood, it appears to have many similarities with the path to criminal gang involvement, albeit that it's participants would suggest a more noble cause.

However, the same element or issues may be at play, and include personal and group identity, the human dynamic about group involvement and belonging, the youthful need to do something that you see that has meaning, the desire to support the "underdog", the desire to strike back against the

oppressors (whether that's government, community or even family). These and similar attitudes, beliefs, or issues may be present in the path to violent extremism or terrorism.

Some community based policing strategies have been successful in reaching into communities to counter gang recruitment and in the same vein, opportunities may exist to use some of the features of community based policing to counter recruitment efforts of violent extremism or terrorism. Given that such activities can only continue in a community in which there is either tacit approval or ambivalence, community based policing has the ability to create an environment in which such activities are under scrutiny by the entire community, and in which the police response to them would be widely supported and even desired.

Community based policing has many strengths and facets that can create not only strong communities, but which can also help with combating violence extremism and terrorism.

However equally, community based policing has many facets or strategies which when improperly employed can be a divisive force in a community, and which can drive a wedge between elements within a community.

In this discussion, when contrasting various community policing approaches and their ability to impact upon countering violence radicalism and terrorism, we will do so in a paradigm in which all the critical elements of government, police structure, resources and community engagement are in place.

However, even positively intentioned community policing initiatives can produce harmful results if they are not carefully implemented and monitored. As with any community based policing undertaking, the national and local governance structure needs to support the ability for the community to become engaged in their own security and for them to engage with the police. Repressive or totalitarian regimes cannot engage the community in a positive manner and seek their participation in community safety.

Community engagement

The issue of community engagement is the first, and arguably the most critical and high-risk element of community based policing as it relates to terrorism. If the intention is to engage members of the Muslim community in community safety, there are both risks and concerns.

Community engagement should include activities to seek dialogue with community members, to have them identify their concerns, and to discuss options, resources and strategies to reduce risk, crime and disorder. However, if the community is in transition, there is the possibility that Muslims that are new community members are not welcome, potentially due to ethnic or religious intolerance. Further, new community members may not have engaged with neighbours or community groups, due to lack of awareness, language barriers, or cultural difference and therefore may not be reached through informal community contacts or through formal broadcast channels.

Therefore, community policing efforts may be undertaken without ever contacting new community members that may also be at the greatest risk. Local community officers, in collaboration with other community resources, need to monitor community demographics, and the community “temperature”, to ensure there is broad based engagement and no groups are excluded.

Community cohesion

The police may seek to draw upon the unity or cohesiveness of the community, where members have concern for each other’s safety and property. However, as with community engagement, the strength of community cohesion can also represent a barrier to newcomers with different cultures, languages and religion. The shifting strategies related to the issue of community cohesion within the UK display the many facets and challenges related to this issue. In 2011, an analysis of the Home Office Prevent programmes and the CONTEST and CONTEST II initiatives included community cohesion building as one

of its three major pillars (Innes et al. 2011). However only a few years later in 2015 the Prevent strategy review concluded that the Home Office Prevent strategy and cohesion programmes must remain distinct (Secretary of State for the Home Department 2011). This is further contrasting by the UK National Council of Voluntary Organizations (Jochum et al. 2005), whose publication consciously uses the terms “social cohesiveness”, to address the relationship between people, versus the potential barriers that could exist with the group-think affiliated with community cohesion.

Understanding the community and reaching out to the rights people.

Community policing always runs the risk of failure if it is seen as disingenuous. If the local government, the police service or the police officers involved are view as being opportunistic or where there is seen to be an alternate agenda, the community or elements of the community may become disengaged. Even if there is a perception of commitment, the police service and the involved officers have to display a level of understanding of the community, of its structure, hierarchy and how issues are generated and identified. When working within one’s own ethnic community this knowledge and understanding is intuitive, and as such the ability to extend this to other cultures and ethnic communities may not be well understood. However, if local police officers are assigned to a community, and expected to utilize community based policing strategies, but are unaware that there are differences in family structure, roles within the family, community power relationships, the role and relationship of a faith, faith leaders and places of worship, then officers may be asking the wrong questions of the wrong people. This in turn can be seen as either creating a power shift, or of developing service delivery strategies based upon invalid information. Within the Muslim community, this is most obvious in the desire to identify a faith leader. Christian and Jewish faith leaders are also the prayer leaders, and the people that the faithful turn to for guidance, support and validation. However in the Muslim faith, the Imam may not have the

same role, and that roles varies between nations and even communities. However, the Masjid Council, who selects and appoints the Imam, has significantly more influence over the community. However, the public discourse and rhetoric of governments, politicians and the police focuses on the need to engage in dialogue with Imam's, and the positive and negative role that various Imam's play in the Muslim community. As a result, there is little discussion about the actual role of the Masjid Council in the local Muslim community, and as a result, local community officers may inadvertently be putting their time and effort into engagement with the Imam, which could be less effective than discussions with the members of the council.

We can imagine an external visit who is the agent of an organization with significant wealth, arriving in the UK to determine where funding and resources should be allocated. Unfamiliar with the nuances of government in the UK, they turn to a bin collector on the street, a position revered in their own community, asking them to provide guidance on funding allocation, while ignoring the Prime Minister and the Cabinet. The reaction would be hostile and disengaging, along with a sense of outrage, indignation and insult.

When local police officers do the same thing in the communities they police, should we be surprised when we illicit similar reactions from the impacted communities.

Policing focus (immigration versus local crime)

Immigration enforcement is always a contentious issue within immigrant communities. Invariably, people have arrived as visitors, with the intention of remaining in the country to escape issues ranging from poverty to repression. Many immigrants function "below the radar screen", having not secured "legal" immigrant status within the country. However, such people usually remain in fear of being discovered by the government enforcement agents, and they will obviously avoid contact with the

police for fear of being deported. Therefore, the role of immigration enforcement agent has put local community officers out of touch with the communities they police. As a result, police services such as Toronto (Canada), have a general policy not to make inquiries about a person's immigration status, unless there is a bona fide reason (Quan 2015), such as when the person has committed a crime and an immigration warrant may exist.

In the United States, the President Task Force on policing recognized that building trust and legitimacy remains an elusive challenge for their policing community, and their report recommends that "...state and local law enforcement should not be involved in immigration enforcement." (President's Task Force on 21st Century Policing 2015).

Engaging does not mean acquiescing

Local police officer, politicians and community leaders also have to listen to the various sectors of the community, however that doesn't always mean that they must acquiesce to community wants and demands, but rather that those wants and desires must be taken in context.

As an example in a community in rural Ontario, the local Doctor was under investigation and surveillance by the provincial police for having grown marijuana and making it available to patients using it for pain management, instead of forcing patients to go through the regular extensive bureaucracy.

When area police officers arrived to conduct the investigation, a large number of community members lined the main street of the small town to decry the police action. Clearly the community and the police were at odds over the focus of their enforcement activities. If the community is opposed to the enforcement activity, and the police no longer have the confidence of the community in their activity, their ability to serve the community is impacted.

However this concept is counterbalanced with events such as the policing of the Selma to Montgomery Alabama marches of 1965, where local citizens were opposed to the action and enforcement activities of the federal law enforcement officers. In this case the federal agents were viewed as having no legitimacy within the local community, and their enforcement activities were radically opposed by the local community and the local police. However, there was a broader national and international agenda that needed to be considered. If the federal agents had acquiesced to the demands of the local community, broad lawful institutional racism would still be in place in the southern United States. The role of the police, at the local, regional and national levels, includes being aware of the local concerns, but they must also put those concerns in context. For community officers however, their actions may put them in opposition to groups within their local community, where they will be required to balance ethical issues, local interests and national interests, any or all of which they may find are in opposition.

Dialogue, communications and information

During the G20 demonstrations in Toronto, the Canadian Security and Intelligence Service (CSIS) was monitoring a spectrum of terrorists and violent extremist groups. Their observations of area mosque and interview with members of the Muslim community was causing great concern for the Muslim Community across Toronto. However, when community leaders were brought together with the author, senior South Asian police leaders and Muslim officers, and provided a detailed briefing of the CSIS activities, as well as the preparations of the Toronto Police and information about what to expect during the event, community apprehension was greatly decreased. Despite all the other event that transpired during the event, the local Muslim community did not participate in lodging any complaints against the Toronto Police Service.

Police and Education

The community based policing strategy of police involvement in public education ranges from early school education through to engagement in senior year, and to outside the school environment to information sessions for new citizens on their obligations and what they can expect from the police, can have a profound impact on the community. The police participation in public education can have a positive and profound impact on the community. Positive engagement with the police in the school environment and the availability of the police officer as an information resources can have a positive effect on students. In the UK, the utilization of police officers trained in counter-radicalization to talk to at-risk youth in the schools is part of the national Prevent strategy (Secretary of State for the Home Department 2011).

Conclusion

Many of the community policing strategies used to combat crime and community disorder have great value in helping combat violent extremism leading to radicalism and terrorism. However, in all cases these strategies have to be carefully implemented and monitored in any community. Whether the goals is crime reduction, community order or countering violent extremism and terrorism, evidence based strategy selection, thoughtful planning, implementation monitoring, and program evaluation will continue to be critical components of a successful community based policing strategy.

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